

HIERARCHICAL MODIFICATION OF FLAX FIBRES BY ZINC OXIDE NANOSTRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

To improve the adhesion at the interphase in natural fibre-reinforced composite materials, ZnO nanorods were grown by a hydrothermal treatment on flax fibres surface. The synthesis methodology is a two-step process, where the ZnO nanorods were grown from a ZnO nanoparticle seed layer deposited on the flax fibre surface. Several parameters can affect the final hexagonal nanorods morphology but in this work the investigation was focused on the number of seeding cycles, growth time and replacement of the growth solution. From TGA analysis is evident that the degree of coverage is higher at longer growth time (5 hours), without a significant decrease in the mechanical properties. The characteristic peaks of ZnO observed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) indicated the growth of ZnO nanorods on the surface of flax fibres with an hexagonal wurtzite structure. It is concluded, by SEM micrographs, that highly oriented and well-aligned ZnO nanostructures can be grown on flax fibres after 5 hours of treatment and with the change of the solution every 2.5h. This novel ZnO interface shows potential for engineering the interfacial strength of flax fibre composites, thus making them suitable for a wider range of applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the field of fibre-reinforced composite materials, the most commonly used reinforcements are glass and carbon fibres. In recent years, due to growing environmental concerns and the constant demands for the development of sustainable materials, natural fibres have gained momentum as reinforcement in composite materials for engineering applications, due to their recyclability and environmentally friendly origin [1,2].

The enormous growth of bio-composites is indicative of their wide application as next-generation semi-structural materials. Natural fibres are cheap with low density, as well as readily available and with mechanical properties that are comparable to those of glass fibres [3,4].

Flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) is one of the most widely used biofibres and is extracted from the stems of the flax plant. The main constituents of a flax fibre are cellulose, hemicellulose, wax, lignin and pectin, in varying quantities; consequently, the microstructure of a flax fibre is extremely complex due to the hierarchical organization at different length scales and to the variable proportions of chemical constituents [5]. Cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin are fundamental components that determine the physico-mechanical properties of fibres where cellulose is the stiffest and strongest organic constituent in the fibre. However, cellulose is a semicrystalline polysaccharide with a large amount of hydroxyl groups, which confer hydrophilic nature to the natural fibre when used to reinforce hydrophobic matrices. This incompatibility is the main problem of polymeric composites reinforced with natural fibres. The result is the formation of weak bonds between the fibre and the polymer and a poor

interfacial strength [6]. The hydrophilic characteristics of natural fibres lead to high moisture uptake that lowers the tensile properties of the fibres, thus reducing the mechanical performance of the resulting bio-composites.

As a result, modifications of natural fibres through specific treatments are certainly necessary. To improve the interfacial fibre / matrix bond, chemical modifications for flax fibres have been considered. Alix et al. [7] performed various chemical treatments, such as maleic anhydride (MA), acetic anhydride (Ac), silane (Si) and styrene (S), on flax fibres to investigate their effects on the tensile properties of fibres and found that chemical treatments reduced fibre stiffness.

Thus, an alternative approach must be considered. Indeed, to increase the surface area for bonding and enhance load transfer between fibre and matrix, one possibility is to grow nanowires, nanotubes or microscale whiskers on the surface of the fibre that could protrude into the matrix. The whiskering process involves the nucleation and growth of single high-strength crystals such as silicon carbide (SiC), titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) and zinc oxide (ZnO).

Many approaches have been used to fabricate ZnO nanostructures, such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD), hydrothermal processing, electrochemical deposition, and magnetron sputtering, with and without a catalyst [8]. ZnO nanowires have been generally synthesized by chemical or physical vapor deposition but require high temperatures (≥ 350 °C) and sophisticated equipment; on the contrary, the hydrothermal process adopts a low-temperature aqueous growth synthesis in order not to damage the fibre, hence preserving its mechanical properties. For this reason, the hydrothermal process used to grow ZnO nanostructures has been enormously successful due to its simplicity and mild growth conditions [9-11].

The hydrothermal growth method typically follows a two-step process, which involves an initial seeding of ZnO nanoparticles layer on the surface and a subsequent solution deposition process, with consequent development of epitaxial crystals of ZnO nanowires. The dimensions, the shape and the degree of crystallinity can be modulated by the synthesis parameters such as the concentrations of the precursors, the temperature and the duration of the synthesis [12].

ZnO has three typical crystal structures: wurtzite, zinc blende, and rock salt. The thermodynamically stable phase of ZnO at ambient temperature and pressure is wurtzite, which shows an hexagonal structure with both Zn and O atoms arranged in a hexagonal close-packed pattern and stacked alternately along the c-axis. The morphology of ZnO can be modified through variation of the growth solution's properties and consequently, this method offers new opportunities to engineer the interface for improved strength.

The variety of nanometric zinc oxide structures means that they can be classified among new materials with potential applications in many fields of nanotechnology. Zinc oxide can occur in one (1D), two (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) structures. The four most common types of 1D ZnO nanostructures are nanowires, nanorods, nanobelts, and nanotubes [8].

The present work aims to grow ZnO nanostructures, through a low-temperature hydrothermal process, on the surface of the flax fibres with a view to improving interfacial adhesion when used as reinforcement in natural fibre composites. The hydrothermal process involves two separate steps, the seed and growth, where parameters such as number of seed cycles, growth times and replacement of growth solution will be analysed in order to optimize the hexagonal nanorod-like morphology.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Individual flax yarns have been extracted by hand from Biotex fabric. The Biotex flax fabric (*Linum usitatissimum*) is a 2x2 twill fabric (200 g/m²), commercialized without any specific sizing agent and supplied by Composites Evolution (UK). Analytical grade reagents of zinc acetate dihydrate (Zn(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O, 99%), zinc nitrate hydrate (Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, 99%), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 99%) and hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA, 99%) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used without any further purification. The absolute ethanol (CH₃CH₂OH, 99.8%) was supplied by VWR Chemicals and the 18 MΩ·cm Milli-Q water was used through the experimental steps.

2.2 Methods

ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized following the two-step methodology proposed by Hu et al. [13]. In the synthesis are involved two processes: the initial formation of the seed layer and the growth of ZnO nanorods through nucleation.

For the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticle seeds, 1 mmol of zinc acetate dihydrate was dissolved in 80 mL of ethanol at 50 °C and vigorously stirred for 5 min. A separate solution of 2 mM sodium hydroxide was dissolved in 100 mL of ethanol at 50 °C and stirred vigorously for 5 min. Both solutions were then cooled to room temperature. Upon cooling, 40 mL of zinc acetate solution was added to 320 mL of ethanol, and 40 mL of sodium hydroxide solution was added to 100 mL of ethanol. The solutions were heated separately to 65 °C then mixed together under vigorous stirring at 65 °C for 30 min. The flax yarns and twill fabrics were rinsed with ethanol and dried at 150 °C for 10 min. The ZnO nanoparticle seeds were coated on the fibres by dipping them into the solution followed by annealing at 150 °C for 10 min. This step was repeated one (1S) and three times (3S).

For the ZnO nanorods growth process, 3.71 g of zinc nitrate hexahydrate and 1.75 g of hexamethylenetetramine were dissolved in 500 mL of 18 M Ω -cm Milli-Q water and heated to 90 °C under vigorous stirring. Once the solution reached 90 °C, the yarns and the fabrics were immersed in the beaker containing the growth solution. At fixed times, the solution was changed, and the samples were put in another beaker with preheated growth solution. At the end of the growing step, the samples were rinsed with 18 M Ω -cm Milli-Q water to remove the presence of precipitates. The fibres were withdrawn at different growth times to characterize their morphologies.

2.3 Characterizations

The morphology of the ZnO nanostructures was analysed by FE-SEM, a field-emission scanning electron microscope (Tescan MIRA3). All specimens, singles yarns and twill fabrics, were sputter coated with chromium prior to each FE-SEM observation to ensure a good conductivity and to improve the quality of the micrographs.

Surface wettability tests were performed measuring the contact angles of water droplets on the twill fabrics surface using an optical analyzer (OCA15Pro, DataPhysics Instruments, Filderstadt, Germany). The static sessile method with a droplet volume of 3 μ L was selected and a Milli-Q ultrapure water was used as testing liquid. A minimum of ten droplets localized on different areas of the flax fabric samples were analysed. Contact angle values were determined by drop shape analysis using the DataPhysics SCA 20 software module.

The analysis of the degree of surface coverage was carried out by measuring the mass loss of ZnO coated- flax fibres using a SetSys Evolution TGA/DSC (Setaram Instrumentation) thermogravimetric analyser. The fibres were placed in an alumina pan and heated at a rate of 10 °C/min to a maximum temperature of 800 °C in argon atmosphere.

The identification of the crystalline materials was performed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis by means of Philips X'Pert PRO powder diffractometer. XRD patterns were collected in the range of $2\theta = 10^\circ - 80^\circ$ with a step width of 0.01° and a counting time of 7 s per step. The employed radiation was monochromated $\text{Cu}_{K\alpha}$ (40 kV – 40 mA).

A mechanical characterization of the ZnO coated - flax fibres has been carried out by performing tensile tests on single flax yarns. The single yarn tensile tests were performed according to ASTM C-1557. Three different gauge lengths were tested, namely 20, 30, and 40 mm. Individual yarns were glued onto card tabs with a central window cut-out to match the desired gauge length for the test. Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature with a Zwick/Roell Z010 equipped with a 1 kN load cell. Tests were performed in displacement control with a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. Before testing, all the yarns were heat treated at 45 °C for 24 h for moisture elimination. Thirty yarns were tested at each gauge length.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To understand the different morphologies that could be obtained with the two-step synthesis methodology mentioned before, at first it was decided to fix the numbers of seed cycles at 3 (3S) and the growing times at 1, 3, 4 and 6 h, while changing the solution every hour. Typical morphologies obtained as a function of determined growth times are reported in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1: SEM micrographs of ZnO nanostructures deposited on the yarn and the contact angle measured on the twill at 1 h (3S) of growth time.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of ZnO nanostructures deposited on the yarn and the contact angle measured on the twill at 4 h (3S) of growth time.

From SEM characterizations it is evident that the flax fibre surface is covered by a continuous and densely packed array of ZnO nanostructures. In Fig. 1 the hexagonal rods, a few micrometres long and hundreds of nanometres in diameter, provide the flax fabric with a quasi-superhydrophobic behaviour (contact angle close to 130°) in contrast to pristine flax fabrics. With increasing growth time (Fig. 2), the morphology changed and ZnO nanorods appear as bundles of smaller diameter nanorods showing lower contact angle (110°). The first experimental results may imply that the reaction time is crucial for the formation of the desired hexagonal nanorod crystal structures [14].

As the synthesis route is a two-step methodology it was decided to investigate if the nucleation process, where occurs the formation of a thin layer of ZnO nanoparticles on the substrate, could promote or hinder the formation of the hexagonal nanorods morphology. For this reason, it was decided to reduce the number of seed cycles from 3 (3S) to 1 (1S) with growing times fixed at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 hours, while changing the solution every hour.

To understand which are the parameters that influence the formation of the oriented hexagonal nanorods, it was studied the growth kinetics by SEM micrographs, X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). In Figure 3 are reported the different morphologies obtained at different times, in comparison with the neat flax fibre (Fig. 3a).

Figure 3: FE-SEM micrographs at different magnifications of flax fibres untreated (a) and treated with ZnO nanostructures with 1 cycle of seed process: (b) 1 hour of growth time (20 µm and inset 2 µm); (c) 2 hours of growth time (20 µm and inset 1 µm); (d) 3 hours of growth time (20 µm and inset 1 µm); (e) 4 hours of growth time (20 µm and inset 1 µm); (f) 5 hours of growth time (20 µm and inset 2 µm).

From Figure 3 it can be noticed that the growth duration is an important factor to control the size of the final ZnO nanostructure. As shown in Fig. 3b, in early stages of crystal growth (1h) oriented structures were not formed. From 2h on, there is the onset of the crystals growth with mostly rounded-shape crystals nanoparticles (Fig. 3c). After 3 hours of growth, hexagonal nanorods with vertical orientation were observed (Fig. 3d-e-f). It is evident that after a long period of growth the hexagonal nanorods became much more oriented and able to cover most of the yarn surface, while at the beginning of the nucleation the crystals are not well formed and randomly oriented [15].

Moreover, the XRD pattern confirms the presence of ZnO wurtzite structure at long growth times (Figure 4).

Figure 4: X-Ray diffraction patterns of the untreated flax fibre (black line) and the ZnO-coated flax fibres at different growth times (1-2-3-4-5 hours).

The diffractions were carried out on the twill flax fabrics treated with the same conditions of the single flax yarns (Fig.3) and the results show that there is the presence of three well-defined sharp peaks related to the presence of cellulose in flax fibres; furthermore sharper diffraction peaks with longer growth times are evident, which correspond to the hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO, confirming that the crystallization of hexagonal crystals is favoured at higher reaction times [16]. The intensity of the peaks for crystalline ZnO increases with increasing growth time of the ZnO nanorods.

The number of seed cycles seems to play a fundamental role in the final morphology obtained; indeed lowering the number of seed cycles, from three to one, appears to favour the formation of more regular and ordered nanostructures (hexagonal wurtzite nanorods), without the formation of other less common morphologies (bundles of smaller diameter nanorods, Fig. 2) as confirmed by SEM images and XRD results.

In order to obtain a final product with good mechanical properties and a high interfacial adhesion, it is necessary to have, not only a regular and homogeneous morphology, but is also crucial to get a high degree of ZnO coverage over the entire fibres. From the SEM micrographs the samples treated at 3-4-5 hours (Fig. 3d-e-f) showed the highest degree of coverage, probably due to the longer reaction times that allowed to coat better the fibres [17]. To confirm this hypothesis, TGA analysis was performed on neat flax fibres and on the treated samples at different reaction times (1-2-3-4-5 hours) in order to determine the thermal behaviour of ZnO-flax samples (Figure 5).

Figure 5: TGA thermogram of the different samples coated with ZnO at different growth times.

The main weight loss detected by TGA measurement is between 250-450 °C and is related to degradation of the cellulosic substances (mainly hemicellulose and cellulose) present in flax fibres [18].

The amount of ZnO grown on the surface of the flax fibres was estimated from the difference in mass loss of the nanorod-decorated flax fibre and the bare flax. The TGA analysis shows the highest residue mass (32%) for the sample treated at 5h, probably due to the higher degree of ZnO nanorods deposited on the surface of the flax fibres. In comparison with the residual mass of the neat sample (12%), the residual weight was increased by 20% for the sample at 5h; these conditions allow the greatest growth of ZnO on the fibre. Moreover, there is a direct correlation between the reaction times and the residual mass: at short time corresponds a low residual mass, indicating that the flax fibres are not well covered with ZnO nanorods, as confirmed also by FE-SEM micrographs (Figure 3).

Tensile properties of flax fibres are essential when considering their use as reinforcement in fibre reinforced polymer composites. The mechanical properties of natural fibres are influenced by many factors, including the plant origin and growth conditions, fibre extraction method, fibre diameter, fibre surface treatments, humidity (RH), etc. Single yarn tensile tests were performed on the commercial flax yarns and on the treated fibres at different reaction times; the results are reported in the Table 1

Flax fibres	F_{max} (N)
Neat flax fibre	22.97 ± 3.94
1h	18.90 ± 4.28
2h	16.42 ± 3.29
3h	21.12 ± 4.18
4h	16.55 ± 3.07
5h	23.38 ± 3.91

Table1. Tensile force as a function of growth time for flax yarns as obtained from single yarn tensile tests.

No significant variations in terms of force (N) between neat flax fibres and treated ones were detected. This is important because underlines that the hydrothermal treatments these fibres undergo are not detrimental to their mechanical properties.

As a result, the treated flax fibre that shows the best results in terms of morphology, degree of ZnO coverage with the hexagonal wurtzite structure and that maintains good mechanical properties is the sample treated at 5h, with the change of the solution every hour and one seed cycle.

As it is believed that with the passage of time the OH⁻ would continuously hydrolyse in the water solution from HMTA up to a certain time and then the OH⁻ would be consumed [17], it appears useful to investigate if there is an effect produced by the replacement of a new growth solution. Three syntheses were performed with 1 seed cycle and 5 h of growing but with different solution replacement conditions: one without any refill of the solution (FF5h_0), one with the refill every hour (FF5h_1) and one with the refill at 2.5 hours (FF5h_2.5). The resulting morphologies were analysed by FE-SEM and the results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: SEM micrographs of flax yarns as a function of growth solution replacement: (a) 5h_0, (b) 5h_1 and (c) 5h_2.5.

The morphology was found to be significantly affected by the replacement of new growth solution. Fig. 6a shows the formation of undefined round-like shaped nanoparticles demonstrating that the replacement of the solution, with these synthesis conditions, is necessary to grow hexagonal nanorods of ZnO on the fibre surface.

In Figures 6b and c, with the refill of the growth solution every hour and after 2.5 hours, respectively, it is evident the formation of the hexagonal ZnO nanorods. In both cases, the ZnO nanorods are uniformly deposited onto the flax surfaces; the diameter of the upper face of the hexagonal nanorods in sample FF5h_1 is in the range of 50-100 nm, whereas in sample FF5h_2.5 (Fig. 6c) the diameters are in the range of 100-200 nm, but with a higher coverage density and vertically aligned.

As the morphology seems better and more regular in the sample treated at 5h with the replacement of growing solution at 2.5 hours, it was decided to perform the single yarn tensile test with three different gauge lengths (20-30-40 mm) in order to characterize the mechanical behaviour of the ZnO-

flax fibres as a function of the length of the flax yarns. The mechanical properties of the yarns are reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Peak force as a function of gauge length for the sample FF5h_2.5

Generally, a higher tensile strength is observed for fibres with a shorter gauge length (20 mm vs. 40 mm) [19]. In other words, the tensile strength decreases with an increase in fibre length: the longer the fibre, the higher its probability of containing a defect (e.g. kink bands). As the test length increases, the number of weak links or imperfections also increases, thus resulting in reduction in tensile strength [20]. In the present case gauge length does not seem to adversely affect, in a significant way, the tensile properties of flax yarns. Figure 8 shows a comparison of peak forces for flax yarns with the optimized ZnO nanostructures.

Figure 8. Breaking force for neat flax fibres, FF5h_1 and FF5h_2.5.

Comparing the results from tensile test for the neat flax yarn, the flax yarns decorated with ZnO at 5h with refill every hour and the flax yarns coated with ZnO at 5h with refill of the solution at 2.5 hours, it is evident that there were no variations in the values of the maximum force. The mechanical properties confirm that the steps involved in the hydrothermal treatment for the surface modification with hexagonal ZnO nanorods do not sacrifice the tensile properties of the underlying fibre, thus suggesting the use of ZnO-flax yarns as reinforcement in composite materials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

ZnO nanorods were successfully grown on the surface of flax yarns and fabrics using a low-temperature hydrothermal method to improve their interfacial compatibility with polymer matrices.

The reaction time plays a crucial role in the final morphology obtained. XRD displayed the characteristic peaks for crystalline ZnO, which indicated the successful growth of ZnO on the surface of the flax fibres and the intensity of the ZnO peaks increased with increasing growth time.

The degree of coverage increases as a function of growth time as confirmed by residual weight compared to untreated flax fibres. The hydrothermal treatments do not seem to affect the tensile properties of the ZnO coated fibres, while the replacement of the growth solution at well-defined intervals was found to markedly affect the resulting ZnO morphology. In this regard, the best condition can be achieved by changing the solution every 2.5 hours for a total growth time of 5h.

In conclusion, as the morphology of the ZnO nanorods can be accurately controlled, the interface of flax fibre reinforced composites can be tailored to meet the requirements of specific applications with the possibility to add further functionalities such as photocatalytic activity.

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